

GREI Metadata Recommendations from DataCite schema version 4.6

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Overview

One goal of [GREI](#) is to support interoperability and discovery of datasets across repositories by establishing common metadata standards for the generalist repositories. Having focused on an agreed standard, the [DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6](#), the GREI Metadata working group has set its Year 4 goal for repositories to build on their existing work on metadata for research datasets.

Version 1 of these metadata recommendations strongly encourage repositories to collect specific metadata when researchers publish their research outputs, including data from NIH-funded projects. It can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101956>.

The GREI Metadata Task Group has continued to press for better interoperability as the project continues. As such, the working group has created this V2 set of recommendations to strongly encourage that each repository member collect the following metadata to support the generalist repository use cases for sharing, discovering and tracking the impact of data.

We also hope this common metadata schema will be useful for data repositories beyond GREI to improve interoperability across data repositories and across the NIH data landscape.

Recommendation

The document lists strongly encouraged metadata to be collected by each GREI repository in alignment with the metadata collected by DataCite's optional metadata properties. Where applicable, the values and vocabularies that repositories are encouraged to use have also been reviewed by the subcommittee and included in the recommendations.

While these are the recommendations of the subcommittee to-date, the goal of the subcommittee is for the recommended common schema to evolve based on community feedback, new use cases, and emerging community initiatives to allow for updates and additions to the strongly recommended fields in the future.

For DataCite's property definitions, cardinality/quantity constraints, and other usage notes, see [DataCite Metadata Schema 4.6](#)

DataCite element ID	DataCite-Property	Subcommittee recommendations about property values
1	Identifier (Mandatory)	<u>DataCite generated DOI</u>
2	Creator (Mandatory)	
2.1.a	nameType	Use controlled list values from DataCite: "Personal" or "Organizational".
2.2	givenName	
2.3	familyName	
2.4	nameIdentifier	For names of people, use ORCID IDs . For names of organizations, use ROR IDs .
2.4.a	nameIdentifierScheme	For names of people, use "ORCID". For names of organizations, use "ROR".
2.4.b	schemeURI	For names of people, use ORCID's URI, https://orcid.org/ For names of organizations, use ROR's URI, https://ror.org/
2.5	affiliation	Use names of organizations from the Research Organization Registry (ROR) .
2.5.a	affiliationIdentifier	Use IDs from ROR in URL format (e.g., https://ror.org/05h1kkg64).
2.5.b	affiliationIdentifierScheme	Use "ROR".
2.5.c	schemeURI	Use ROR's URI, https://ror.org/
3	Title (Mandatory)	
4	Publisher (Mandatory)	
5	PublicationYear (Mandatory)	
6	Subject	<u>The appropriate controlled vocabulary depends on the domain covered by the dataset; see the discussion below.</u>
6.a	subjectScheme	
6.b	schemeURI	

6.c	valueURI	
8	Date	
8.a	dateType	Use controlled list values from DataCite. All datasets should contain the date type Issued to indicate the publication date; other dates may provide additional context, such as Available or Collected.
8.b	dateInformation	
10	ResourceType	
10.a	resourceTypeGeneral	Use controlled list values from DataCite; <u>for datasets the appropriate value is "Dataset"</u>
12	RelatedIdentifier	
12.a	relatedIdentifierType	Use controlled list values from DataCite
12.b	relationType	Use controlled list values from DataCite; <u>the recommended values and the recommended terminology to use in the user interface is described below</u>
12.f	resourceTypeGeneral	Use controlled list values from DataCite.
15	Version	
16	Rights	
16.a	rightsURI	
16.b	rightsIdentifier	
16.c	rightsIdentifierScheme	
16.d	schemeURI	
17	Description	
17.a	descriptionType	For general descriptions of the deposit, select the descriptionType "Abstract" from DataCite's controlled list.
19	FundingReference	
19.1	funderName	
19.2	funderIdentifier	Use IDs from ROR.

19.2.a	funderIdentifierType	Select "ROR" from DataCite's controlled list.
19.2.b	schemeURI	Use https://ror.org/
19.3	awardNumber	
19.4	awardTitle	

GREI Recommended Subset of Relation Types

The DataCite controlled list of types is very thorough and flexible; in practice a subset of this list is sufficient for most purposes. In addition, the names in the DataCite Controlled list are appropriate as an enumerated list for encoding metadata, but may not be appropriate for interactions with users. Accordingly, the table below provides the recommended types and terminology to use for most common interactions.

Researcher-Friendly Label	DataCite relationType	Use Case
Cited by this article	IsCitedBy	Dataset is cited in an article, that is not the original description of the dataset
Cites this work	Cites	Dataset cites or references a paper or another dataset
Supports this material	IsSupplementTo	Dataset is supplementary to other material (e.g. publication)
Supported by these materials	IsSupplementedBy	Other materials (e.g. software) are supporting this dataset
Part of a larger project	IsPartOf	Dataset belongs to a broader collection, grant, or study
Includes other parts	HasPart	Dataset contains related datasets or components
Updated version of	IsNewVersionOf	Dataset is a new version of a previously published dataset
Older version of	IsPreviousVersionOf	Dataset is a previous version of a new published dataset

Has Version	HasVersion	As a canonical dataset (e.g. for an ongoing observational study or other research project) the Dataset may have versions of the data with version-specific DOIs
Is a Version of	IsVersionOf	The dataset version is a specific version of a canonical dataset
Duplicate of another record	IsIdenticalTo	Dataset exists in multiple repositories or records
Collected using this instrument	IsCollectedBy	Dataset gathered by specific instrument

These values are intuitive, align well with scholarly practices, and are supported by tools such as [DataCite Event Data](#) and initiatives such as [Make Data Count](#).

Recommendations for Controlled Vocabulary Integration in Generalist Repositories

We recommend the use of controlled vocabularies wherever possible. The criteria listed below can help in the selection of a vocabulary. We further recommend the use of a broad, general vocabulary to facilitate comparisons across domains, such as the [OECD Fields of Science and Technology](#). A more granular, domain-specific vocabulary, such as MeSH, can also be employed as necessary.

Controlled Vocabularies Quality Criteria

- Governance: Vocabulary has clear governance, maintenance processes, and versioning
- Coverage: Provides adequate coverage of relevant domains
- Granularity: Offers appropriate level of specificity for the content being described
- Currency: Regularly updated to reflect evolving terminology
- Persistence: Maintains stable identifiers with a commitment to long-term support
- Machine-actionability: Available in machine-readable formats with semantic relations
- Documentation: Well-documented with clear definitions and usage guidelines

Implementing Controlled Vocabularies in the Repository Interface

The technical implementation of controlled vocabularies significantly impacts their usability and effectiveness. Repositories should aim for implementations that:

- Provide Search and Browse Functionality: Allow users to search and browse datasets using controlled vocabulary terms.
- Offer Auto-completion or Suggestion Features: Assist depositors in selecting terms by providing suggestions from the controlled vocabularies as they type.
- Clearly Display Applied Terms: Make the controlled vocabulary terms used to index a dataset easily visible to users.

Leveraging the Metadata Center and Community Efforts

The [CEDAR Metadata Center](#) is a valuable resource for information on metadata standards and best practices, including those related to controlled vocabularies. GREI repositories should explore the resources and guidance available through the Metadata Center to inform their controlled vocabulary strategies.

MeSH for Subject Classification for NIH-Funded Research

Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) vocabulary, maintained by the National Library of Medicine.

- Recommended Vocabulary: MeSH (Medical Subject Headings)
- Scheme URI: <https://meshb.nlm.nih.gov>

MeSH is widely adopted in biomedical literature and offers broad, hierarchical coverage of health and life sciences topics. Its use will support alignment with other NIH resources, including PubMed and clinicaltrials.gov. Importantly, we propose MeSH as a recommendation, not a requirement, to allow flexibility for datasets outside the biomedical domain or for repositories already using other structured vocabularies.

Complementary Vocabularies by Domain

Repositories should support additional vocabularies based on the domains they serve. For example:

- Gene Ontology (GO): For gene functions, cellular components, and biological processes
- NCBI Taxonomy: For organism classification
- Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (ChEBI): For chemical compounds
- Disease Ontology: For human disease concepts

For specialized needs, consider:

- HIVE (Helping Interdisciplinary Vocabulary Engineering): Provides access to multiple vocabularies through a single interface

Proposed CRediT Role Subset for Generalist Data Repositories

GREI repositories increasingly seek to recognize the varied contributions involved in dataset creation, curation, and sharing. The [CRediT taxonomy](#) provides a standardized framework for contributor roles, offering a path toward better attribution and metadata consistency.

Some efforts have happened to customize CRediT to data use cases, such as the [WSL Data Credit project](#). However, the authoritative list of 14 roles adopted by [NISO](#) do not specifically state how they map into our space.

This document proposes a subset of official CRediT roles that are most relevant for generalist data repositories to implement.

Current Authoritative CRediT Roles (NISO)

1. Conceptualization
2. Data curation
3. Formal analysis
4. Funding acquisition
5. Investigation
6. Methodology
7. Project administration
8. Resources
9. Software
10. Supervision
11. Validation
12. Visualization
13. Writing – original draft
14. Writing – review & editing

Proposed Subset for Generalist Repositories

We recommend supporting the following subset of roles, which most directly apply to the lifecycle of dataset generation, curation, and publication:

- Conceptualization – Identifying the research goals behind the dataset.
- Data curation* – Managing, cleaning, and preparing data for sharing and reuse.
- Investigation* – Performing the experiments or data collection.
- Methodology – Designing the processes that guided data collection or analysis.
- Project administration – Overseeing project execution, including data management planning.
- Software* – Writing code or scripts used to generate or prepare the data.
- Supervision* – May refer to oversight of data collection or project execution, typically by senior researchers, PIs, or data managers. However, this role is often implicit or institutional rather than individually documented during dataset submission.
- Writing – original draft – Drafting associated documentation, such as README files or metadata.
- Writing – review & editing – Reviewing or improving documentation and descriptive metadata.

The following roles may be relevant in specific contexts, depending on repository policies or contributor preferences:

- Formal analysis – May be useful for attributing those who derived or created secondary datasets.
- Funding acquisition – Often not applicable unless funders require attribution or the principal investigator’s role is explicitly recognized.
- Resources – May apply when someone acquires equipment, recruits subjects, or provisions instruments used in data generation.
- Validation* – May involve confirming the quality, accuracy, or reproducibility of data. While important, formal validation is not always part of the dataset deposit process.
- Visualization – May refer to generating visual representations of data (e.g., charts, maps, dashboards). These are often created outside the repository workflow or auto-generated, making attribution inconsistent.

The ones denoted with * are those that map directly to the [WSL Data Credit project](#). The first subset aims to strike a balance between completeness and feasibility, making it easier to implement structured attribution without overburdening depositors. However, the full list can also be used.

ORCID Recommendations

Collection of ORCID iDs

Good: Allow users to enter ORCID iDs manually for corresponding authors only.

Better: Enable collection of ORCID iDs for all authors, including coauthors.

Best: Collect ORCID iDs for all authors and coauthors through authenticated ORCID sign-in.

Rationale: Collecting iDs for all contributors ensures comprehensive attribution and enhances discoverability across systems that rely on ORCID metadata.

Authentication of ORCID iDs

Good: Accept manually entered ORCID iDs without verification.

Better: Allow users to optionally authenticate their ORCID iDs.

Best: Require authentication via OAuth to ensure that iDs are valid and owner-approved.

Rationale: Authenticated ORCID iDs reduce errors and impersonation risk, and they enable seamless integration with downstream workflows.

Push to ORCID Registry

Good: Offer users the option to link their ORCID and manually update their record.

Better: Automatically push relevant deposit metadata to the ORCID record (with user consent).

Best: Allow users to manage ORCID permissions, including what data is pushed and when, via a dedicated dashboard or settings interface.

Rationale: Direct integration improves the completeness of researchers' ORCID profiles and supports open infrastructure by enriching public metadata.

Full ORCID integration represents a relatively low-cost, high-impact improvement for generalist repositories. While implementation requires coordination across product, engineering, and policy teams, adopting "best" practices supports researcher recognition, enhances metadata quality, and advances open research goals.

Recommended Usage of 'Dates' in GREI Metadata

Dates help users understand when a dataset was collected, created, published, or updated. They also shape how metadata is indexed, cited, and discovered. To support consistency across GREI repositories, this guide outlines how to use the Date and dateType fields in the

[DataCite Metadata Schema](#), with a focus on interpreting and labeling dates in a way that is useful and accurate for both humans and machines.

Issued - Labeling the Publication Date

All GREI repositories should use the Issued date to represent the Publication Date of a dataset.

- This is the date the dataset was formally published or released via the repository.
- It should appear as the Publication Date on the dataset landing page and in any metadata exposed to downstream systems.

```
{  
  "date": "2024-10-15",  
  "dateType": "Issued"  
}
```

This field is required for every dataset.

Recommended Additional Dates

You can include other dateType values to give more context about the dataset lifecycle. Here's how to use them:

dateType	Use when...	Example
Created	The dataset was assembled or finalized	Final file completed in September 2024
Available	The dataset became publicly accessible	After embargo ended
Submitted	The dataset was submitted to the repository	Before internal review
Accepted	The dataset was formally accepted	After QA or curation review
Collected	Data was gathered from instruments, fieldwork, or surveys	Samples collected from March 1-15, 2024
Coverage	The dataset describes a specific time period	Covers 1950-2000 weather data
Updated	The dataset was revised, replaced, or versioned	New version uploaded in April 2025
Withdrawn	The dataset was removed from public view	Include reason in the description

Implementation Tips

- Use Issued for Publication Date (required)
- Use ISO 8601 format: YYYY-MM-DD or ranges like YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD
- Include multiple dateType entries if they provide useful context

- Use Updated to indicate dataset revisions
- Use Collected and Coverage carefully—these have different meanings

What to Avoid

- Don't use Available instead of Issued—they're not interchangeable
- Don't leave Issued out—this is the date that gets indexed and cited
- Don't rely on Other unless absolutely necessary (and if you do, use dateInformation to explain)
- Don't confuse when the data was collected (Collected) with what time it describes (Coverage)

Example Metadata Block

```
j
"dates": [
  {
    "date": "2024-10-15",
    "dateType": "Issued"
  },
  {
    "date": "2024-09-30",
    "dateType": "Created"
  },
  {
    "date": "2024-03-01/2024-03-15",
    "dateType": "Collected"
  },
  {
    "date": "2024-10-15",
    "dateType": "Available"
  }
]
```

Specific Use Case: When Metadata Are Public Before the Data

Datasets are routinely deposited in GREI repositories where metadata are immediately available, but the actual data files are restricted (e.g., under embargo or pending article publication). At a later date, the data files become publicly accessible.

How to Handle Dates in This Scenario

Step 1. Submitted

Use this to record when the dataset was first submitted to the repository. This helps mark the start of repository involvement.

```
{  
  "date": "2024-08-01",  
  "dateType": "Submitted"  
}
```

Step 2. Issued

Use this to represent the official Publication Date, aligned with when the dataset is formally published by the repository—typically when metadata first becomes visible to the public. This is the date to expose as the Publication Date on the landing page and for citation purposes.

```
{  
  "date": "2024-08-10",  
  "dateType": "Issued"  
}
```

Step 3. Available

Use this to indicate when the data files themselves become available to download (i.e., embargo ends). This provides clarity to users and downstream systems that there was a delay between metadata visibility and data access.

```
{  
  "date": "2024-11-01",  
  "dateType": "Available"  
}
```

Optional: Add an Embargo Note

You can also include a short embargo notice in the metadata description, indicating the reason or condition for the delay:

```
"description": "Metadata publicly available as of 2024-08-10. Data files released after journal publication on 2024-11-01."
```

Summary of 'Dates' Recommendations

- Always use Issued to represent the Publication Date This is the date to show on landing pages and in citations.

- Add other dateType values, when possible, (Created, Submitted, Available, etc.) to provide context and clarity about the dataset’s lifecycle.
- Use Submitted, Issued, and Available together when metadata are public before the data. This helps clearly communicate embargo periods.
- Follow ISO 8601 formats (e.g., YYYY-MM-DD) for consistency and machine-readability.
- Avoid common pitfalls, such as using Available in place of Issued, or confusing Collected with Coverage.
- Be transparent about embargoes. Add a note in the description to explain when and why data access is delayed.

Well-structured use of dates improves discoverability, supports reuse, and ensures that datasets are properly cited and understood across GREI repositories.

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